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European Journal of Experimental Biology, 2016, 6(4):20-22

Food and Feeding Habits of *Teraponjarbua* from Coringa Mangrove area of East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh, India

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ABSTRACT

*The present study was investigated and analysis the stomach of *Teraponjarbua*. Fish specimens collected from the Five different placeless of Coringa Mangrove area East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh, India. From July 2012 to June 2013. The sample stored in boxes containing Ice. The stomach analysis was carried out using frequency of occurrence and numerical methods. The stomach showed verity of food particles were grouped into categories in following order. Copepods, Molluscanveligers, Decapods, Polychates, Fish eggs & Larvae, Cheatoghathes, Adult Crustaceans, Cirripidnaeplei, Miscellaneous.*

Key words: Food and Feeding Habits of *Teraponjarbua*, Stomach Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Teraponjarbua Family common fish from Coringa Mangrove area. Feeding ecology is an important aspect of the life history strategy of a species to within their ecosystem (Blaber, 1997; Haji Samal et al., 2003). Without knowledge of the food requirements, feeding behavior pattern and predator- prey relationship is not possible to understand the predicted changes that might result from any natural or anthropogenic intervention (Hajisamae et al., 2006). The biology of details of gut content analysis was various researchers (Jayaram, K. C., 2009). Numerous researcheshave been conducted about food and feeding ecology of many fish species and seasonal changes in feeding habits (Hvnes. 1950; Hvslob. 1980). *Teraponjarbua* are the predator-prey pyramid within fresh water as well as in marine water.

The aim of this study was to investigate the type of food eaten by *Teraponjarbua* studies could be important in the rational management of this species was expresses as percentage of the total number of food items found in the stomach. In the frequency of occurrence method. The occurrence of food items was expressed as the percentage of the total number of species.

Methods of Sampling

Most of the sampling was collected from the seine catches and gill net catches from Chollangi, Matlapallem, Ramanapallem, Coringa and Bhairavapallem. Collected were made at water with regular collection in a year at intervals of 30 days each. After collection the fish were stored in Ice boxes the gut carefully removed and preserved in 5% formalin. The stomach contents were later analyzed in the laboratory, stomach contents of different groups encountered their percentage of groups encountered their percentage of occurrence was calculated. The material of

organic matter beyond the state of identification was taken together as miscellaneous whose percentage composition was also noted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The various food items recoded from the stomach of *Teraponjarbua* during the study period are presented in the Table-I. Generally the food items found in the examined stomachs were groups into Eight categories namely Copepods, Molluscanveligers, Decapods larvae, Polychaete larvae, Fish eggs and larvae, Cheatognathes, Adult crustaceans, Cirripidnaeples, and Miscellaneous.

Copepods

The bulk of the fish diet the highest percentage was recorded in the month of April (90.10%). In low percentage was recorded in the month of May (62.45%).

Molluscanveligers

Molluscanveligers formed most abundant item in the gut content analysis. The highest percentage occurrence in the month of August (21.73%). In low percentage was recorded in the month of January (1.90%).

Decapods larvae

The maximum percentage occurrence of decapods larvae was recorded in the month of March (8.29%) and minimum percentage was recorded in the month of April (0.70%).

polychaete larvae

The maximum percentage occurrence of polychaete larvae was recorded in the month of May (2.61%) and minimum percentage was recorded in the month of July (0.18%).

Fish eggs and larvae

The maximum percentage occurrence of Fish eggs and larvae was recorded in the month of April (1.67%) and minimum percentage was recorded in the month of October and May (0.33%).

Cheatognathes

The maximum percentage occurrence of Cheatognathes was recorded in the month of April (0.88%) and minimum percentage was recorded in the month of October, November, December, January, February, March and April (0.0%).

Adult crustaceans

The maximum percentage occurrence of Adult crustaceans was recorded in the month of March (2.82%) and minimum percentage was recorded in the month of September (1.07%).

Cirripidnaeples

The maximum percentage occurrence of Cirripidnaeples was recorded in the month of October (0.07%) and minimum percentage was recorded in the month of April (0.03%).

Miscellaneous

The maximum percentage occurrence of Miscellaneous was recorded in the month of March (0.05%) and minimum percentage was recorded in the month of September and October (0.01%).

Table: Month-wise Zooplankton quality analyses in the study area during July 2012 and June 2013

	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June
Biomass	1.94	4.49	0.7	0.63	0.51	0.42	1.27	0.81	1.37	1.37	0.93	1.03
Copepods	71.41	68.12	75.33	72.93	88.55	84.07	85.59	79.56	70.61	90.10	62.45	88.57
Molluscanveligers	20.96	21.73	17.29	17.25	4.66	3.74	1.90	8.06	14.03	2.09	20.31	5.18
Decapods larvae	4.40	5.32	2.99	5.24	2.23	1.23	3.73	7.52	8.29	0.70	1.79	0.75
Polychaete larvae	0.18	0.63	0.26	0.66	0.52	0.63	0.30	0.51	2.61	0.86	1.01	0.19
Fish eggs and larvae	0.44	0.46	0.42	0.33	0.59	1.26	3.03	1.42	0.33	1.67	1.31	0.52
Cheatognathes	0.1	0.88	0.51	0.13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.25	0.09
Adult crustaceans	1.20	2.14	1.07	1.79	1.81	2.63	1.64	1.19	2.10	1.87	2.82	2.04
Cirripidnaeples	0.60	0.27	0.28	0.77	0.13	0.27	0.61	0.34	0.62	0.03	0.20	0.67
Miscellaneous	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.04

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